

Deliverable 2.6

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: 2-AGES, 36-
INSA

Contributing partners: 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS,
25-NUIG, 33-NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6		
WP and task	WP2, JRP15-R2-WP2-T3 ; JRP15-R2-WP2-T6		
Leader	2-AGES, 36-INSA		
Other contributors	2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI		
Due month of the deliverable	M46		
Actual submission month	M54		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 15.06.2022		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See updated Grant Agreement</i>		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>	
	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>		
	EFSA <input type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input type="checkbox"/>	EEA <input type="checkbox"/>
	EMA <input type="checkbox"/>	FAO <input type="checkbox"/>	WHO <input type="checkbox"/>
	OIE <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Other international stakeholder(s):		
	Social Media:		
	Other recipient(s):		

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6

16S METAGENOMICS RESULTS: MICROBIAL BIODIVERSITY AND PHYLOGENETIC RELATIONSHIPS OF ARB OVER ECOSYSTEM BOUNDARIES (T2.3, T2.6)

I. Introduction

1. Description of the tasks JRP15-R2-WP2-T2.3 and JRP15-R2-WP2-T2.6

The Deliverable D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6 (16S metagenomics results: Microbial biodiversity and phylogenetic relationships of ARBs over ecosystem boundaries (T2.3, T2.6)) comprises task JRP15-R2-WP2-T3 and JRP15-R2-WP2-T6.

As part of task JRP15-R2-WP2-T3 (Assess microbial and ARG diversity with NGS in the selected test environments (metagenomics). Compare microbial and ARG diversity between ecosystems and over ecosystem boundaries. Characterization of cultivable environmental bacteria on complete nutrient and minimal media) and task JRP15-R2-WP2-T6 (Assess clonal/lineage diversity in selected ARB species), all sample collectors performed 16S shotgun metagenomics (V1-V9) in order to assess the microbial diversity between compartments, countries and time-points in the extracellular but also in the total DNA.

These results are being correlated now with the ARGs obtained via gene enrichment (Task JRP17-R2-WP2-T3.2), the heavy metals, herbicides and antibiotic residues of WP4.

Data collected via questionnaires given to the farmers about the farmers themselves and the animals is being used to assess factors contributing to the ARGs diversity. In addition, we have cultivated the samples to obtain bacterial isolates and characterized them phenotypically and genetically.

2. Tasks modifications

In the original task JRP15-R2-WP2-T6, phylogenetic trees using 16S amplicon sequencing and the shotgun sequencing data were planned. However, since the number of samples that the consortium analysed was higher than the initially planned, the methodological approach was modified and no phylogenetic analysis will be done using the raw data (FASTQ). Nevertheless, this change in the methodology has allowed us not only to address the original research questions stated in the project proposal, but we have gained more statistical power due to the increase in the sample size. Although it could be possible to re-analyse the 16s and ARG data from the raw FASTQ files obtained from the outsourced company, we obtained no

phylogenetic information, but only the tables with 16S and ARG identities. Due to the number of samples a re-analysis would take time and computation resources that are unfortunately not feasible at the moment. In addition, participating institutes cannot pre-analyse and preformat their own samples/sequences, since we opted for a harmonized analysis that has been performed by the „WP2- analysis team“.

3. Deliverable description

3.1. 16S shotgun sequencing (V1-V9)

After assessment of DNA quality, genomic DNA samples were processed with a 2-stage PCR workflow (Qiaseq 16S/ITS panel, QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany). The first PCR step incorporated a phased primer pool to enrich for conserved regions of the 16S gene. Following a cleanup with magnetic beads, library amplification then introduced sample indices and ensured that sufficient target was present for NGS. Following a final cleanup, libraries were quality controlled and quantified. Ready-to-sequence libraries were sequenced on an Illumina platform using 2x 300 bp paired-end sequencing. All samples were demultiplexed and Illumina adaptor residuals trimmed using cutadapt v2.6, followed by read length thresholding. The DADA2 (1.18.0) pipeline was used to construct the amplicon sequence variant (ASV) table, a higher-resolution analogue of the traditional operational taxonomic unit (OTU) table. Taxonomic classification was determined using the SILVA rRNA reference database v138. Cross-contamination occurring throughout library preparation was not detected.

After cleaning up the data by removing chloroplasts, mitochondria, all OTUs with no reads and correcting some errors we ended up with 573646 OTUs in 476 samples. We then proceeded to create a Phyloseq object with the available data (McMurdie & Holmes, 2013). Because Ares Genetics (the company that did the sequencing and initial analysis) did not do the sequence alignment we could not include a phylogenetic tree in the Phyloseq object and preform analysis that depend in it.

We divided the samples into 11 compartments:

- Crop – crops harvested in the agricultural fields;
- Feed – proceed feeds for animal consumption;
- Farmers – feces samples from farmers;
- Pigs_Barn – feces from farm pigs;
- Manure – feces of pigs and other organic material used to fertilize the soil;
- Wild_animals – feces samples of wild animals like deal, hares, sheep and goat;
- Soil_Fs_Ms_Ctrl_Bline – soil samples from forests, meadows and agricultural fields before being cultivated or fertilized;
- Soil_field_noMan – soil samples from agricultural fields fertilized without the use of manure;

- Soil_field_Man – soil samples from agricultural fields fertilized with of manure;
- Water_DRG – water samples from drainage, river and ground water;
- Water_WTP – water samples from waste treatment plants;

Briefly, Austria had the highest number of samples, followed by Portugal and Estonia. Portugal and the United Kingdom had more extracellular DNA samples than total DNA; Austria and Estonia were balanced and Ireland and the Czech Republic had more total DNA samples. Concerning compartments, soil samples were the most common, with 46.9% of the samples. All compartments presented an even number of total and extracellular samples. Also, the distribution of the samples in the different sampling dates was very heterogeneous. Extracellular DNA had much more samples that did not pass the quality control and this explains the differences between countries. It is of note that Water_DRG was the only compartment exclusively with samples that did not pass the quality control.

Since we had a high percentage of zeros in the majority of the samples, we chose 1000 reads as a cutoff to try to limit the number of samples. Samples with less than 1000 reads were removed but they did not constitute a large percentage of any compartment. This was the only data manipulation done before alpha diversity.

For the other analysis, we also used prevalence filtering by removing OTUs with less than 3 reads in 99.5% of the samples. This reduced the percentage of zeros in the remaining samples. To reduce further the number of OTU's to simplify the subsequent analysis, we did an aggregation by genera and ended up with 455 samples and 1866 genera.

When separating the data sample type we observed 232 samples and 1725 genera for extracellular DNA samples and 223 samples and 1810 genera in total DNA samples.

The Phyla in extracellular and total DNA samples were dominated by Proteobacteria and Firmicutes. Phyla represented 93.5% and 94.9% of the reads in extracellular and total DNA, respectively. Phyla with less than 1% of the total reads were aggregated in the "other" category. Most of the Phyla were present in both extracellular and total DNA samples. We observed Phyla with a high percentage of total reads by compartment, namely Acidobacteriota, Chloflexi and Gemmatimonadota, which had higher reads in soil samples, while Bacteroidota and Firmicutes had higher reads in farmers, pigs, manure and wild animals samples.

Regarding alpha diversity, we observed that soil samples from forests, meadows, controls and baselines were significantly different than the other soil samples in extracellular DNA, but not in total DNA. In both types of samples, soil with and without manure did not present significant differences while manure was always significantly different from any soil sample.

Before we did ordination and differential abundance analysis, we transformed the data using centered log ratios (CLR), which removes the compositional constraints to make the standard multivariate techniques suitable for analysis (Quinn et al., 2019).

For the ordination analysis we used the Aitchison distance (Gloor et al., 2017; Quinn et al., 2019). We started by separating the extracellular from the total DNA samples. We then used the CLR transformation performed by ANCOM-BC. Next, we used function "prcomp" to perform the principal component analysis and used ggbiplot to create biplot and 3D plots. In both extracellular and total DNA samples PC1 separated soil samples from everything else, PC2 and PC3 separated the other compartments. The first three principal components explained 41.6%, 8.9% and 4.0% of the data variability in extracellular DNA samples and 45.2%, 7.3% and 5.3% in total DNA samples.

For both extracellular and total DNA samples, the Permanova test rejected the null hypothesis, meaning that either the centroid and/or the spread of the objects is different between the groups. Permadist test rejected the null hypothesis of no difference in dispersion between groups so the result of Pernanova may be due to different dispersion in the different compartments.

We tried to do pairwise comparisons using pairwise Permanova and Tukey's honest significant

differences test. The results are unreliable because the uncertainty that the significant differences obtained derive from actual difference positions of the compartments centroids or due to differences in dispersion.

For the differential abundance analysis we used multiple differential abundance methods to help ensure robust biological interpretations. We choose ALCOM-BC, ALDEx2 and the Wilcoxon test with CLR transformation. We choose ANCOM-BC over ANCOM because the former is computationally simpler and faster to implement (Lin & Peddada, 2020b). ALDEx2 and the Wilcoxon are also computationally inexpensive and well positioned in tests with different differential abundance methods (Lin & Peddada, 2020b, 2020a). Wilcoxon test has also included to compare an older method to the new ones. Results showed the percentage of differential expressed OTUs and percentage of reads of differential expressed OTUs for the Wilcoxon test and for ANCOM-BC. For ALDEx2, some comparisons between compartments failed. For all analysis, the results suggest a similarity between the three soil compartments, with low percentages of differential expressed genes and reads. For the remaining compartments, the conclusions are not that clear and the dendrograms cluster them in different ways, depending on the methodology used.

It should be said that this study had problems with the water samples, that could be explained by the technical difficulties that we found in these samples. For example, all Water_DRG samples failed quality control.

Finally, we will try to understand how OUT's passes between compartments. For that we constructed heatmaps with modified OUT tables that only show if an OTU is present or absent from one compartment, for extracellular and total DNA samples. After the samples and compartments are reorganized according to the heatmaps dendrograms, we hope to see what OUT's are shared or are unique to the different compartments. In both extracellular and total DNA samples, the compartments are divided into two main groups that separate the soil samples from everything else, was in the ordination analysis. The remaining samples are further divided into two groups: one with the mammals, another with the crops, feeds and Water_DRG. Water_WTP and manure seem not to cluster with anything else.

Concerning the separation for the OUT's, the situation is more complex. There are separations that are common to the extracellular and total DNA and others that are specific. In both types of samples, we note large OUT's clusters exclusive from soil, others that are exclusive from manure and others exclusive for Water_WTP. Following the group order in the dendrogram for the OUT's in the total DNA samples, we can see a first cluster shared by mammals and manure, another that is shared by mammals, Water_WTP, manure and soil samples. These are followed by a cluster shared by every compartment. Next, we see several clusters that are difficult to attribute a characteristic.

References

- Gloor, G. B., Macklaim, J. M., Pawlowsky-Glahn, V., & Egozcue, J. J. (2017). Microbiome Datasets Are Compositional: And This Is Not Optional. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 8(NOV), 1–6. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2017.02224
- Lin, H., & Peddada, S. Das. (2020a). Analysis of compositions of microbiomes with bias correction. *Nature Communications*, 11(1), 3514. doi:10.1038/s41467-020-17041-7
- Lin, H., & Peddada, S. Das. (2020b). Analysis of microbial compositions: a review of normalization and differential abundance analysis. *Npj Biofilms and Microbiomes*, 6(1), 60. doi:10.1038/s41522-020-00160-w
- Quinn, T. P., Erb, I., Gloor, G., Notredame, C., Richardson, M. F., & Crowley, T. M. (2019). A field guide for the compositional analysis of any-omics data. *GigaScience*, 8(9), 1–14. doi:10.1093/gigascience/giz107

3.2. Characterization of cultivable bacteria

More than 300 clinically-relevant bacterial isolates belonging to the species *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *S. enterica*, *S. aureus*, *E. faecium* and *E. faecalis* were obtained after sample

cultivation by the six participating countries. Also, nearly 200 isolates belonging to other bacterial species, mostly environmental were gathered by the partners. The clinically-relevant isolates were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility and paired-end sequenced was carried out on Illumina devices at the institutes. Afterwards, raw genome sequences (FASTQ) were forwarded to 2-AGES for genome assembly, species re-identification, species-specific assessment of the genetic relatedness by core genome MLST using publicly available schemes, extraction of the sequence types of the classical MLSTs, and extraction of ARGs and virulence genes using CARD and VFDB databases, respectively. Afterwards, the assemblies (FASTA) were forwarded to 33-NVI to extract the mobile genetic elements as well as re-extraction of ARGs and VGs using the DTU server tools (Mobile genetic elements finder, ResFinder and Virulence Finder, respectively).

Regarding clinically-relevant species, cgMLST-based analysis showed intra-country clusters, but no multicountry cluster was detected. However, several STs were detected in more than one country, especially among the *E. coli* isolates. In all countries, isolates retrieved from wastewater, pig manure and pigs were those carrying more ARGs, including extended-spectrum beta-lactamases, but also ARGs associated to antimicrobials used in animal husbandry such as aminoglycosides, tetracyclines or sulfonamides.

The analysis of associations between ARGs in the isolates and the different compartments and countries is still **ongoing**. The identified mobile genetic elements will provide more information about the possible dissemination via horizontal gene transfer of ARGs and VGs between clones of the same or different species, countries and compartments.

3.3. Characterization of ARGs obtained via gene enrichment and sequencing

DNA quality was assessed in a similar manner as carried out for 16S sequencing, and metagenomic DNA was hybridised with biotinylated molecular probes developed based on the ARESdb database of antimicrobial resistance, virulence and stress resistance genes. After hybridization, the target DNA were captured using magnetic beads coated with streptavidin, and the DNA that was not captured was washed away. The enriched DNA sample was then released from the magnetic beads and used for the construction of sequencing libraries. Through this method, a several-fold increased in the number antimicrobial resistance, stress resistance and virulence genes can be obtained. ARG-enrichment data was obtained from 475 samples and 6652 different resistance, virulence and stress resistance genes were detected across the dataset.

The analysis of the gene-enriched sequence data has started with samples obtained from Ireland, as this represents a more restricted set of samples which facilitates data exploration. A large diversity of AMR, stress resistance and virulence genes was encountered. Wastewater sludge samples had a greater diversity (higher Chao1 and Shannon indexes) of target genes than from wild deer faeces. Extracellular DNA from wastewater had a high diversity of ARGs, with aminoglycosides, beta-lactamase, multidrug resistance and tetracycline resistance comprising the main AMR types detected. By contrast, deer faeces ARGs were dominated by ARGs classified as „mutation or variant antibiotic target“. There was little variation in the

diversity and abundance of AMR genes in wild deer faeces across the 7-month sampling period.

We encountered some irregularities with the AMR gene names, particularly regarding their classification into different AMR groups, which has necessitated a revision of the gene names and classification. For this reason, the bioinformatic and statistical analyses of the main set of gene enrichment data with all the compartments across all participating members was delayed.